

SIMULATION OF TWO-DIODE MODEL BASED PV SOLAR CELL / ARRAY: A SIMULINK APPROACH

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Abstract:

This work proposes a Simulink-based Model of a photovoltaic (PV) system using the two-diode model of a PV solar cell. The series and shunt resistance of the solar cell are estimated in this model by an efficient iteration method. The number of required input parameters are four and are based on the available information from the PV module datasheet. The developed model allows the user to predict a PV cell's current-voltage and power-voltage characteristics curves by varying sunlight, cell temperature, ideality factor and series resistance value. The model is also applicable under partial shading/ module mismatch condition. The characteristics curves obtained by the simulation of the proposed model are matched with the data provided by the manufactures.

Key words: Simulink, Two-Diode, PV module, Cell Temperature, Irradiance, Ideality Factor, Shading.

I. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the potential long-term benefits and various attractive benefits provided by the government, commercialization of large and small scale photovoltaic (PV) power generation becomes increasingly popular in many countries. Since the PV power systems involve the installation of high cost PV modules, the guarantee of the optimal usage of the available solar energy must be ensured through an accurate and reliable simulation of the designed PV systems prior to the installation. This simulation requires the PV cell modeling by which the nonlinear I-V and P-V characteristics curves have been estimated.

Till to date, a number of PV cell models has been developed in the literature. The simplest model is the single-diode model [1-4]. This impractical model needs only three parameters: the short-circuit current (I_{sc}), the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and the diode ideality factor (α). Inclusion of a series resistance (R_s) improves the accuracy of the single-diode model [5-10]; but, these models are incapable of handling temperature variations. An additional shunt resistance (R_p) significantly improves the model efficiency [11-15] at the expense of higher computational overheads. Such models suffer from decreased accuracy under low-irradiance (G) levels, especially near V_{oc} [16].

The recombination loss in the depletion region of a solar cell can be modelled by an additional diode [17]. Although this two-diode model increases the number of parameters, this model improves the accuracy, since the recombination loss becomes substantial for a realistic solar cell, especially under low voltages. The main challenge is, therefore, to develop a two-diode model with reasonable simulation time while maintaining the accuracy as high as possible. The works [18-20] proposed several techniques; but all these techniques have suffered from two major problems: 1) increased computational cost due to introduction of the new additional coefficients and 2) difficulties in the determination of the initial values of the parameters.

Some models [21-23] used physical characteristics parameters i.e. diffusion coefficient, lifetime etc. to describe the two-diode model. However, the information about these parameters are not always available in commercial PV datasheets and hence, these models are not feasible for the PV designers. There are also some software packages (i.e. PV-Spice, PV-DesignPro, SolarPro, PVCad and PVsyst) available in the market for PV system simulation. But all these packages are expensive, complex and unable to interface the PV arrays with power converters [24]. K. Isahaque et al. [16] recently proposed a PV system simulator based on the MATLAB-Simulink environment. This model uses four input parameters which are available on a standard PV module datasheet to reduce the computation time and estimates the values of R_s and R_p using an efficient iteration method. However, instead of using separate simulink block for each component of the output current, this model first takes all the required inputs and constants into a masked simulink subsystem and then calls MATLAB functions for all the components of output current. Therefore, due to a number of function calls, this model is slower in simulation than it requires if each component current were calculated from a corresponding Simulink block. This work addresses this issue and attempts to improve the simulation time by eliminating the function calls through the implementation of Simulink blocks.

II. ANALYSIS

Fig. (1) represents the more accurate two diode model of a photovoltaic (PV) cell. Based on this model, the

non-ideal PV cell output current can be expressed as

$$I = I_{ph} - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

where I_{ph} , I_{D1} , I_{D2} and I_{sh} are the light generated photo current, the current due to the diode action (corresponds to the diode D1), the current due to the recombination process in the depletion region (corresponds to the diode D2) and the shunt current respectively and can be expressed as [16]

Fig 1 Two-Diode PV cell model

$$I_{ph} = I_{sc} + K_I (T_c - T_{ref}) G \quad (2)$$

$$I_{D1} = I_{01} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{\alpha_1 V_T} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$I_{D2} = I_{02} \left[e^{\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{\alpha_2 V_T} \right)} - 1 \right] \quad (4)$$

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V + IR_s}{R_p} \quad (5)$$

where T_c , T_{ref} are the cell temperature and the reference temperature, I_{sc} is the short circuit current, K_I is the short-circuit current temperature coefficient, G is the irradiance, I_{01} , I_{02} are the reverse saturation currents, α_1 , α_2 are the ideality factors for the diodes D1 and D2, V is the voltage across the solar cell, $V_T = KT/q$ is the thermal voltage and R_s , R_p are the series and shunt resistance respectively. From the above equations, it is obvious that R_s , R_p and I_{01} , I_{02} are first to be estimated. Afterwards, using an iteration scheme, the currents in the above equations and hence, the cell current can be determined. The estimation of R_s , R_p is done using Newton-Raphson method in an iteration algorithm as described in the work [16]. As in [16], the computation of I_{01} , I_{02} can be carried by using the following expression:

$$I_{01} = I_{02} = \frac{I_{sc} + K_I (T_c - T_{ref})}{e^{\left[\frac{V_{oc} + K_v (T_c - T_{ref})}{V_T} \right]} - 1} \quad (6)$$

where, V_{oc} is the open circuit voltage and K_v is the temperature coefficient of open circuit voltage, since this expression eliminates the ambiguity in the selection of α_1 and α_2 , avoids the iteration process to compute I_{01} and I_{02} and simplifies the model by setting $I_{01} = I_{02}$.

III. SIMULINK BLOCK DIAGRAMS

The currents I_{ph} , I_{01} , I_{D1} , I_{D2} and I_{sh} can be implemented using Simulink blocks and are shown in Figs (2), (3), (4), (5). The estimated values of R_s and R_p are fed into the "From" blocks along with the datasheet values and the constants. The value of the cell current "I" is fed from the combined simulink block diagram shown in Fig. (6). The iteration process starts by assuming $I=0$ and continues until V becomes V_{OC} . In a typical large PV power system, the cell modules are Fig.d in series-parallel combination ($N_s \times N_p$, where N_s , N_p being the number of cells connected in series and in parallel respectively). The output current equation then can be modified as:

$$I = N_p I_{ph} - N_p I_{01} \left[\exp \left(\frac{V + IR_s \left(\frac{N_s}{N_p} \right)}{N_s \alpha_1 V_T} \right) - 1 \right] - N_p I_{02} \left[\exp \left(\frac{V + IR_s \left(\frac{N_s}{N_p} \right)}{N_s \alpha_2 V_T} \right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V + IR_s \left(\frac{N_s}{N_p} \right)}{R_p \left(\frac{N_s}{N_p} \right)} \quad (7)$$

Where I_{ph} , I_{01} , I_{02} , R_p , R_s , α_1 , α_2 are the individual cell parameters. Fig. (7) shows a building block of a PV array.

Fig2 Simulink Block diagram for the Light-Generated Current, I_{ph}

Fig3 Simulink Block diagram for the Reverse Saturation Current, I01, I02

Fig4 Block diagram for the Diode Currents, ID1, ID2

Fig 5 Block diagram for the Shunt Current, Ish

Fig6 Block diagram for the Output current, I

Fig7 Subsystem block diagram for two diode module

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Verification of Model Data

The model proposed in this work has been validated by the measured parameters of a selected PV module (BP Solar MSX-60). The simulation results obtained with the proposed model and the model of the work [16] are shown in the Table 1 along with the available data of the chosen PV module. From the results, it is evident that, data for the proposed model match very closely with the manufacturer's data.

B. Effect of Cell Temperature

The effect of temperature variation on the output power and the output current is shown in Fig. (8). Since increase in temperature increases reverse saturation current [Eqn. (6)], the total output current and hence, the output power decreases. Fig. (8) shows the same fact.

C. Effect of Irradiance

Effects of the variation of irradiance on the I-V and P-V Characteristics curves are shown in Fig. (9). The curves show that the output current and the power increases with the increase of irradiance. This is due to the fact that increase in irradiance increases the light-generated photo current, I_{ph} [Eqn. (2)]. However, increase in irradiance also increases the open-circuit voltage, V_{oc} ; but this increase is less than that of I_{ph} due to the logarithmic dependence of V_{oc} on G as seen in the following equation-

$$V_{oc} = \frac{\alpha k T}{q} \log \left(\frac{I_{ph}}{I_0} \right) \quad (8)$$

Table 1 Calculated values for some parameters in the proposed model and in the Kashif's Model [16]. Here, $K_v = -80 \text{ mV/oC}$, $K_I = 3 \text{ mV/oC}$, $N_p = 1$ and $N_s = 36$

Parameter	Data Sheet	Proposed Model	Kashif's Model [16]
Isc	3.8 A	3.8 A	3.8 A
Voc	21.1 V	21.1 V	21.1 V
Imp	3.5 A	3.5 A	3.5 A
Vmp	17.1 V	17.1 V	17.1 V
Ipv	-	3.80 A	3.80 A

Fig8 (a)P-V curve. (b)I-V curve for the variation of temperature. Here, $R_s = 0.01 \Omega$, $R_p = 113 \Omega$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p = 1$ and $G = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $\alpha_1 = 1$, $\alpha_2 = 1.2$

Fig9 (a)P-V curve. (b)I-V curve for the variation of irradiance. Here, $T_c = 25 \text{ oC}$, $R_s = 0.01 \Omega$, $R_p = 113 \Omega$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p = 1$, and $\alpha_1 = 1$, $\alpha_2 = 1.2$

D. Effect of Ideality Factor

Effects of the variation of ideality Factor on the I-V and P-V Characteristics curves are shown in Fig. (10). As expected, these Figs show that the output current and the power of a PV array have to increase when ideality factor increases. This is due to the fact that increase in the ideality factor causes the reverse saturation current to decrease [Eqn.s (3) and (4)].

Fig10 (a) I-V curve (b) P-V curve for the variation of ideality factor. Here, $T_c = 250 \text{ C}$, $R_s = 0.01 \Omega$, $R_p = 113 \Omega$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p = 1$ and $G = 600 \text{ W/m}^2$.

E. Effect of Series Resistance

I-V and P-V Characteristics curves for the variation of the series resistance R_s are shown in Fig. (11). From these curves, it is evident that R_s adversely affect the cell performance. This is obvious owing to the fact that R_s increases the diode currents (I_{D1}, I_{D2}) and the shunt current (I_{sh}) [Eqn.s (3), (4) and (5)].performance. This is obvious owing to the fact that R_s increases the diode currents (I_{D1}, I_{D2}) and the shunt current (I_{sh}) [Eqn.s (3), (4) and (5)].

Fig11 (a) I-V curve (b) P-V curve for the variation of Rs. Here, $T_c=250\text{ C}$, $R_s = 0.01\ \Omega$, $R_p = 113\ \Omega$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p=1$ and $G = 600\text{ W/m}^2$.

F. Comparison between Single-Diode Model and Two-Diode Model

Fig.(12) shows the percentage of relative error of maximum power (P) by varying the temperature, the irradiance and for the single-diode model and the two-diode model with respect to the datasheet value. From this Fig., it is evident the two-diode model is more appropriate in predicting the cell/ array performance than the single-diode model.

Fig12 % of Relative Error in maximum power for single-diode model and two-Diode model. Here, $T_c=250\text{ C}$, $R_s = 0.01\ \Omega$, $R_p = 113\ \Omega$, $\alpha_1=1$, $\alpha_2=1.2$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p=1$ and $G = 600\text{ W/m}^2$

G. Effect of Partial Shading

The proposed model is applicable for large system simulation by configuring N_s and N_p . Due to partial shading or module mismatch, multiple local maxima are possible in P-V characteristic curve. Three shading patterns $G_1=100\%$, $G_2=75\%$, and $G_3=50\%$, irradiance/sunlight are considered for grouping the modules. As expected, Fig. (13) shows three maxima corresponding to the shading patterns.

Fig13 P-V curve under shading condition. Here, $T_c=250\text{ C}$, $R_s = 0.01\ \Omega$, $R_p = 113\ \Omega$, $\alpha_1=1$, $\alpha_2=1.2$, $N_s = 36$, $N_p=1$ and $G = 600\text{ W/m}^2$

H. 3-Phase current Conversion

The proposed model is applicable for 3-Phase AC current conversion system. Fig.(14) shows the application of the proposed model in a 3-phase ac load. This load is driven by a system that uses solar panel to produce DC power, which is later converted to ac power. Fig. (15) extends the proposed model to a power grid simply by replacing the 3-phase load with the power grid. Fig.(16) represents the AC output current for 3-phase model.

Fig14 Block diagram for the 3-phase load (AC).

Fig15 Block diagram for the Grid Connected System (3-phase)

Fig16 Output current for the 3-phase load (AC)

V. CONCLUSION

A generalized PV model, which is representative of all the PV cell/module, has been developed with Simulink. The model results are verified with a real PV panel (BP Solar MSX-60)). The proposed model takes the datasheet values (I_{sc} , V_{oc} , I_{mand} and V_m) along with the cell temperature, sunlight/irradiance and ideality factor as input and outputs the I-V and P-V characteristics under various conditions. Since the proposed model is

implemented with Simulink blocks and the required iteration process continues with the feedback loop, it is expected to have faster simulation time than the model developed in [16], where a number of function calls have to be performed.

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